

3D modeling of atherosclerosis progression in coronary arteries

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Abstract— The inflammation and lipid accumulation in the arterial wall represents a progressive disease known as atherosclerosis. In this study, a numerical model of atherosclerosis progression was used. Fluid domain was modeled using Navier-Stokes equations in conjunction with continuity equation, while the solid domain was modeled using Darcy's law. Kedem-Katchalsky equations were used for coupling fluid and solid dynamics. The results of plaque concentration for the left coronary artery were presented in this paper, comparing 2D cross-sections obtained by numerical simulation with original computed tomography (CT) cross sections.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the previous study, wall shear stress and plaque concentration were determined [1], while this research represents the validation of the obtained results. Many studies show influence of the wall shear stress on the plaque progression, because small values lead to the appearance of the first signs of atherosclerosis [2].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plaque progression was performed using numerical approach. Fluid motion in the lumen domain is described with Navier-Stokes equations, the fluid filtration with the Darcy law, while the Kedem-Katchalsky equations used for the solute flow between the lumen domain, endothelium and the first layer of the vessel wall-intima. Blood flow through the 3D model was simulated using PAK solver [2], using physiological values of blood velocity and material characteristics of the wall adopted from literature [3].

III. RESULTS

A three-dimensional simulation of blood flow through lumen and plaque progression in vessel wall was simulated. The bio molecular parameters such as LDL, HDL and triglycerides are used for the computer simulation.

Figure 1 shows a cross-section comparison of CT images and cross sections obtained by numerical simulation.

Figure 1. Cross-section comparison: CT image vs. Computer simulation

The green color in the CT images shows the plaque share in the observed cross-section, while at the same time, on the images of the results of numerical simulations, the presence of the plaque is shown in red color. A good matching of the results can be observed.

By knowing bio molecular parameters such as LDL, HDL and triglycerides, it is possible to predict the sites of plaque occurrence as well as concentration in certain places of the artery using computer simulation. The benefit of this research is a non-invasive approach to assessing the condition of the coronary arteries because using numerical simulations, with a high degree of precision, the size of the plaques in the artery wall can be determined.

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